

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
754702

Country-specific report (case study) Sweden

<https://hejsweden.com/schweden-karte-so-sieht-schweden-von-oben-aus/>

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Categories	Results
<p>Specific legislation</p>	<p>Healthcare Act (Hälso- och sjukvårdslag (2017:30)) https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/halso--och-sjukvardslag_sfs-2017-30</p> <p>Chapter 3 Generally 1 §: The purpose of health care is good health and equal treatment for the entire population. The care should be given with respect for all people's equal worth and for the dignity of the individual. Those with the greatest need for healthcare should be given priority to care. 2 §: Health care services shall work to prevent ill health.</p> <p>Chapter 5 Operations Generally Special obligations regarding children 6 §: When healthcare is given to children, the best interests of the child shall be taken into account. 7 §: A child's need for information, advice and support should be taken into account in particular if the child's parent or any other adult the child lives permanently with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have a mental disorder or mental disability - have a serious physical illness or injury <p>or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are addicts of alcohol or other addictive agents. <p>The same applies if the child's parent or any other adult the child lives permanently with unexpected deaths.</p> <p>Targeted age group: it applies to both adults and children (up to 18)</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation National level</p>	<p>Child Protection Legislation</p> <p>Child protection is dealt with under two different laws: the Social Services Act (Socialtjänstlagen) and the Care of Young Persons Act (LVU).</p> <p>Social Services Act (2001) (Socialtjänstlag (2001:453))</p>

http://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/socialtjanstlag-2001453_sfs-2001-453

Chapter 4 Right to assistance

1 §: Anyone who cannot meet their needs or otherwise receive them is entitled to assistance from the social welfare committee for their support (supply support) and for their life-giving in general.

Chapter 5 Special provisions for different groups

Children and young people

1 §: The Social Affairs Committee shall [among other things]

1. Promote children and young people to grow up under safe and good conditions
3. Carry out outreach activity and other preventive work in order to prevent that children and young get poorly
6. Pay attention to children and young people in environments that are harmful to them

Targeted age group: children are entitled to support if needed, but only children over 15 can ask for support for themselves. For younger children the parent's consent is needed (Chapter 11, §2 and §10).

The Care of Young Persons (Special Provisions) Act (1990) (Lag (1990:52) med särskilda bestämmelser om vård av unga (LVU))

https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-199052-med-sarskilda-bestammelser-om-var-d_sfs-1990-52

If the parents of someone under the age of 18 cannot, for some reason, provide the young person with the support he or she needs, or if the young person her or himself lives a destructive life involving, for instance, substance abuse or criminality, it is possible for such a young person to be cared for according to the Care of Young Persons (Special Provisions) Act.

Targeted age group: children under 18 years old (and under 20 years old in so-called behaviour cases, if this is more appropriate than other care)

The Education Act (2010) (Skollag (2010:800))

http://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/skollag-2010800_sfs-2010-800

<p>Chapter 2 Chiefs and responsibilities 25-28 §§: Student health is supposed to support the student's development towards the educational goals. In the individually targeted work the student health has a special responsibility to eliminate obstacles to each student's learning and development.</p> <p>Chapter 7 School and the right to education Those who are required to attend school 2 §: Children living in Sweden are required to attend school in accordance with the provisions of chapter 7 3 §: According to chapter 2, section 18, section 18, first section of the Constitution, all children covered by the public school have the right to cost-free basic training in public schools.</p> <p>Targeted age group: children under 18 years old</p> <p>Law (1993: 387) on support and services for certain disabled people (LSS) Lag (1993:387) om stöd och service till vissa funktionshindrade) https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-1993387-om-stod-och-service-till-vissa_sfs-1993-387 This Act provides for special assistance and special services for persons with physical or mental disabilities and conditions.</p> <p>Targeted age group: it applies to all age groups.</p> <p>Patient Safety Act (2010); Patientsäkerhetslag (2010:659) https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/patientsakerhetslag-2010659_sfs-2010-659</p> <p>Chapter 6 Obligations for healthcare professionals and others General obligations 5 §: Healthcare professionals should pay particular attention to a child's need for information, counselling and support on the child's parent or any other adult the child lives permanently with</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Has a mental disorder or a mental disability,2. Has a serious physical illness or injury, or3. is addict of alcohol or any other addictive agent <p>The same applies if the child's parent or any other adult the child lives permanently with unexpected deaths.</p>

	<p>Provisions concerning the obligation to report to the Social Council that a child may need the protection of the committee is contained in Chapter 14, 1 § of the Social Services Act (2001: 453). Team (2017: 62).</p> <p>Targeted age group: it applies to both adults and children (up to 18).</p> <p>UNCRC and Swedish law, https://www.government.se/government-policy/childrens-rights/.</p> <p>Targeted age group: children under 18 years old</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Regional level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation National level</p>	<p>In General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The National Board of Health and Welfare has an assignment from the Government to strengthen the support for children as next of kin. Among other things, they promote a family oriented approach, especially in social services, but also in psychiatry. - It is often the case that a situation is not regarded as one related to caring, but is rather related to parenting where a parent has a drug addiction or a mental health condition for example - The Law on Support and Services for Certain Disabled People (LSS) provides support for persons immediately surrounding a disabled person - There is a patchwork of support for young carers. However, children have not been thought about as young carers and they are invisible to a great extent <p>The Healthcare Act</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legislation that says that children have the right to information provides a very good opportunity to talk to the children about support, however, it is though that things could be improved. - Although children have the right to information and the right to participation for example, there is a concern that the child's best interests will not always taken seriously <p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Little is done for children in schools until there is an absenteeism rate of at least 15-20% [Interviewer] - There could be a lot more awareness of children than is currently done

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an individual focus in the Swedish legislation. Working with an adult does not automatically assess whether there are children who are affected or whether the adult needs support with their parenting responsibilities
Enactment of legislation Regional level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are local guidelines that directly prohibit those who provide support to include children and family
Changes in legislation	<p>The Social Services Act (2001)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Law (2015: 982) amended the Social Services Act (2001: 453) - The Social Services Act (Socialtjänstlag (2001:453) is undergoing a review where prevention work has been particularly highlighted - Additional directives are dealing with the elderly and how to ensure that children's rights are clarified and safeguarded in light of the Children's Convention becoming law <p>The Healthcare Act (2010)</p> <p>The organisation Allmänna Barnhuset http://www.allmannabarnhuset.se/ did quite a lot of work on children as next of kin and the regulation in the Health Care Act</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A child's need for information, advice and support should be taken into account in particular if the child's parent or any other adult the child lives permanently with has a mental disorder or mental disability (a) or have a serious physical illness or injury (b) or are addicts of alcohol or other addictive agents (c). <p>United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sweden ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) on 29th June 1990 and a political process led the way to incorporating the Convention on the Rights of the Child into Swedish law - On 13 June 2018, the Riksdag (the Swedish parliament) adopted a bill on making the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child Swedish law. In order for the convention to have a greater impact, the Government is also proposing a guidance document, an education initiative and continued systematic transformation work. It is proposed that the act will enter into force on 1 January 2020. - The Children's Ombudsman has been involved
Specific policy and service frameworks National level	None mentioned
Non-specific policy and	None mentioned

service frameworks National level	
Non-specific policy and service frameworks Regional level	None mentioned
Non-specific policy and service frameworks Local level	None mentioned
Enactment of policy and service frameworks National level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since practice has been specialised and individual focused since the 1970s, the family perspective has been lost a lot. There are sometimes local guidelines that directly prohibit those who provide this support to include children and families. - Changing views about children having their own rights and about their participation is a lengthy process. - There has been a shift in practice with an increase in family counsellors who now have to work with children.
Enactment of policy and service frameworks Local level	None mentioned
Changes in policy and service frameworks	In general terms, over the years children have become viewed with increased agency and as citizens who have rights. Sweden has come a long way in terms of thinking about the impact on children when developing policies. For example, thinking about the child's perspective when building houses or roads.
Recognition of young carers	The term 'young carers' or 'young caregivers' is not used in Sweden. Barn som anhöriga (Children as next of kin or close relatives) is the term used by the Socialstyrelsen, see http://www.socialstyrelsen.se/Lists/Artikelkatalog/Attachments/19114/2013-6-6.pdf ; http://www.socialstyrelsen.se/publikationer2014/2014-5-10 .
Key strengths National level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a well-developed welfare system in Sweden - Swedish legislation has a strong focus on the rights of the child. This has been strengthened further by the Children's Convention. When children know their rights they can probably more easily express their needs. It is commonly believed that children should not take on 'a big responsibility'.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The regulations and framework are open. There are no limitations to providing support and intervening with young carers (i.e. they are not restricted to certain groups). This can also be a weakness. It is therefore reliant upon the individual social secretary or the child protection professional. The same goes for the child protection regulations in the Care of Young Persons Act. - Schools have an obligation to ensure that all children receive the support that they need in order to acquire and complete their education
<p>Key limitations National level</p>	<p>In general</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an unwillingness to accept that the health care sector and social welfare are not taking care of the problems - People in the ministry of social affairs and the National Board of Health and Welfare, they do not want to accept that young people do a lot of caring. - The regulations and frameworks are open. There are no limitations to providing support and intervening with young carers (i.e. they are not restricted to certain groups). It is therefore up to the individual social secretary or the child protection professional. The same goes for the child protection regulations in the Care of Young Persons (Special Provisions) Act. - The regulations in the Young Person's Act 'allmänna råd' [common advice] are really old and are to be updated https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/Lists/Artikelkatalog/Attachments/12728/1997-10-15_1997_15.pdf - There is no definition of when caring roles are 'over the limit' and what is acceptable <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provisions from the Social Services Act state that social services should work with a preventative approach, however, resources have reduced over the years - There is a problem if there are not sufficient numbers of good interpreters. This may therefore lead to the easier option being taken of using children to translate <p>Healthcare Act</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are so many regulations with the Social Services Act. It has become a patchwork and does not have any overview or fit together logically - One regulation of the Healthcare Act relates to thinking about whether there are children involved, but this is not the case automatically with the Law on Support and Services for Certain Disabled People (LSS) or the Social Services Act. However, the Law on Support and Services for Certain Disabled People (LSS) contains provisions on the best interest of the child and the right of children to speak. - The possibility that children could be personal assistants for their parents was removed, illustrating that there is no holistic approach

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a lack of clarity with the Healthcare Act for example, what should be done if parents refuse that information is given to their children and how it relates to the obligation to report to social services - Information that is given to a child has consequences for the child and on their perspective of their family and situation - The parental perspective of a family situation can dominate the child's perspective and parents can withdraw from the investigation process and have the right to deny all kinds of suggestions of support - One problem can be finding out what kind of support children need as relatives - The legislation does not specifically include siblings or parents with developmental disorders [learning disabilities]
Key limitations Regional level	None mentioned
Key limitations Local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As consequence of a lack of resources, the interpretation of legislation can be narrowed at a local level
Evaluation of the current situation National level	<p>In general</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for children as carers is not regulated as it is for adults who are carers - There is an illusion that the welfare state would take care of adults with severe problems. It is therefore not considered that children will need to take care of family members but the reality is different. This is probably an explanation as to why this hasn't been discussed that much in Sweden. - Understanding needs to be developed about what level of caring is inappropriate and this needs to be addressed in policy and legislation - There is a patchwork of provisions that can be used to support young carers but with no clear regulation among the different laws. Children have not been thought about children as young carers - There is a lot of work to be done. Support for the adults or children with care needs should be looked at carefully, rather than supporting children to continue to care - The Swedish systems should guarantee that children are being protected from taking on caring responsibilities and it is possible that this does happen - The Law on support and services for certain disabled people (LSS) should relieve children of caring roles but they may not be always happening in practice - Schools don't understand the issue and do not respond to indicators that there are problems at home due to caring <p>The Children's Convention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Children's Convention may be helpful as it gives a very clear indication that children must be considered in all

contexts

- The Children's Convention will be important. If it just gets attention then healthcare staff will increasingly ask parents if they have children at home

Child protection and children's voices

- There are no specific provisions, but if a young person or child has to take too much responsibility, which leads to a sort of neglect or a vulnerable situation then child protection measure could be taken. But it's not specifically mentioned.
- Children often don't want to be separated from their families. They feel responsible for their families and are not assured that someone else will care for their family
- The provisions in the Social Services Act as well as the child protection regulations in the Young Person's Act are not prescribed, but are very open and not limiting. The key therefore is about awareness and knowledge of the problems for children.
- Once children have taken on the responsibility of caring for a family member and they are removed from the family, they especially worry about the person they cared for
- There is a dilemma as to whether parents have the right to deny accepting support options from society and instead choose to use their children as carers
- Where parents have severe problems, children may not be talked to and asked about their situation. Children's voices could be strengthened a lot more and their views sought
- Whether or not child's perspective is taken into account is not due to lack of legislation but rather down to social workers
- Participation of young people can lead to conflict with parents which in turn can be expensive to resolve

Policy direction

- The focus in Sweden is not on the caring roles of children but more about children as relatives (including their responsibilities)
- Since the 1970's an individualised focus on support has been prevalent - a family perspective has been lost. Some local guidelines directly prohibit support to include children and family
- There is a conflict between family privacy and the interests of children which can result in children with caring roles remaining unseen
- There is a change in direction as to how the problem is being seen with a shift to seeing the child as a partner
- Children as next of kin is a new concept in the Swedish welfare state. The media is needed to awaken the debate.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many municipalities have now concluded that a family perspective is needed - The Social Services Act review which emphasizes preventative work is one way to strengthen the family. With social services more available, children and adolescents might be more likely to ask for help and support and parents may feel they can receive support. A really long assessment is not needed but help should be readily available. <p>Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In relation to the Health Care Act where work is being undertaken with an adult with a serious diagnosis, there could be more awareness of children. Where the problem <i>is</i> noticed, then one tries to help the children - As a result of their experience, family counsellors have become alert to children being ‘next of kin’ - More can be done around awareness of children and supporting the whole family - Professionals firstly need to be aware of the problem and have a method of working to address the problem and support the whole family. Current support systems may work but it can be reliant on capabilities and empathy of individual professionals
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p>Regional level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for the implementation of new policies is not sufficiently in depth to adequately change the understanding of professionals - A clear change in legislation is needed to bring about a broader, family support perspective (whole family approach) as well as adequate support for the person with care needs - Specific legislation for young carers is probably not necessary and could be limiting in a changing society - It’s important to see caring roles for children as something that should be limited and which should not restrict their normal life. This should not however restrict children’s participation. - When assessing adults, parental responsibility and support for children should be included - It’s a problem that the caring roles of children is not recognised - The Healthcare Act requires long-term implementation. One of the main obstacles to implementing it is the competence of adult care professionals in implementing the provision for children. - Children are taking on interpreting roles and more attention needs to be taken so children do not end up in these situations - The Parent Rule really tries to protect and strengthen the children’s position to actually be children - It is down to individual ministers who drive particular policy issues - There are no legal obstacles to working in a more coordinated way it is down to how things are organized

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no holistic approach, but rather a patchwork of regulation that is inconsistent - It is about preventative measures. Children should not end up in these situations at all - Awareness of the issue must still be created - There is a sensitivity about parentification - The law based on the UN convention of children's rights will pass however, the consequences will be 'not so much' since it is without clarity on what it wants to achieve - Awareness of new vulnerable groups takes time
<p>Suggested changes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To include the 'family perspective' within the review of the Social Services Act - Awareness needs to be raised. This could be done by both specifically including young carers in legislation and a goal orientated framework <i>and</i> raising awareness by other means such as information campaigns - Make sure that children are listened to - Perhaps have a more sort of more flexible view on when you become an adult or what comes with becoming an adult - Raise awareness in schools - Update the regulations and handbook in the Young Person's Act (Allmanna rad) to include children as carers as an example of children at risk - Don't support children to continue caring, but look at the shortages in the support for adults and children who need care - If a child is informed that an addiction is a sickness it should also be stated that the parent has responsibility for their actions - Policy and legislation should include what is appropriate and inappropriate caring for children - For the media to wake the debate up - To think more about using the Patient Safety Act in relation to children's needs not being met
<p>Future goals and hopes National level</p>	<p>In general</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Children need to be protected from caring <p>Awareness, understanding and discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More attention is paid to children and youths who support their parents. More information and knowledge is gathered about them including children who are interpreters - Awareness and knowledge about the topic of young carers - For a change in understanding about children as carers and for the issue to be more easily discussed. For mental health and addiction problems to be less taboo <p>Children's voices</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Children’s participation is increased and children’s voices and their rights are taken more seriously - To talk more to children about their views, experiences and their needs and to strengthen the provision in the Health and Care Act of providing children with information <p>Legislation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - That the review of the Social Services Act might lead to a more preventative approach - New legislation will improve organisational approaches with a more whole family approach - To address in legislation those instances where it is not an issue of caring, but where the issue relates to parental capabilities for example arising from a drug addiction or mental health condition of a parent - For professionals to check whether parents with an addiction problem have children and to have contact with those children <p>Accessibility of support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To be in a position where people with care needs are able to receive the support they need and for families to feel they can accept support - There is hope that the Social Services Act can make support from social services more accessible. Support should be preventative, parents should be able to ask for it without fear and children should know they can receive support at an early stage.
<p>Future goals and hopes Regional level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>